

An interior triangle

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We look at the triangles in the figure:

We want to describe the interior triangle in dependence from the exterior triangle. We use the cosine law for $s_c := \overline{CP_c}$, $s_b := \overline{BP_b}$ and $s_a := \overline{AP_a}$:

$$\begin{aligned} s_c^2 &= b^2 + k^2 c^2 - 2bkc \cos \alpha & k \in (0, 1) \\ s_b^2 &= a^2 + k^2 b^2 - 2akb \cos \gamma \\ s_a^2 &= c^2 + k^2 a^2 - 2cka \cos \beta \end{aligned}$$

We apply the sine law:

$$\sin \alpha_2 = \frac{ka \cdot \sin \beta}{s_a} \quad \sin \beta_2 = \frac{kb \cdot \sin \gamma}{s_b} \quad \sin \gamma_2 = \frac{kc \cdot \sin \alpha}{s_c}$$

We introduce 6 new angles:

$$\delta = 180^\circ - \alpha - \gamma_2 \quad \varepsilon = 180^\circ - \beta - \alpha_2 \quad \varphi = 180^\circ - \gamma - \beta_2$$

and:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha' &= 180^\circ - \alpha_2 - \delta = 180^\circ - \alpha_2 - 180^\circ + \alpha + \gamma_2 = \alpha + \gamma_2 - \alpha_2 \\ \beta' &= 180^\circ - \beta_2 - \varepsilon = 180^\circ - \beta_2 - 180^\circ + \beta + \alpha_2 = \beta + \alpha_2 - \beta_2 \\ \gamma' &= 180^\circ - \gamma_2 - \varphi = 180^\circ - \gamma_2 - 180^\circ + \gamma + \beta_2 = \gamma + \beta_2 - \gamma_2 \end{aligned}$$

Now we calculate the sides' segments. We use the the sine law again:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{c1} &= \frac{kc \cdot \sin \alpha_2}{\sin \alpha'} & s_{c2} &= \frac{kb \cdot \sin \varphi}{\sin \gamma'} \\ s_{b1} &= \frac{kb \cdot \sin \gamma_2}{\sin \gamma'} & s_{b2} &= \frac{ka \cdot \sin \varepsilon}{\sin \beta'} \\ s_{a1} &= \frac{ka \cdot \sin \beta_2}{\sin \beta'} & s_{a2} &= \frac{kc \cdot \sin \delta}{\sin \alpha'} \end{aligned}$$

To the interior sides we have the relations:

$$\begin{aligned} a' &= s_b - s_{b1} - s_{b2} \\ b' &= s_c - s_{c1} - s_{c2} \\ c' &= s_a - s_{a1} - s_{a2} \end{aligned}$$

At last we determine the area of the interior triangle:

$$A' = \frac{1}{2} \cdot a' c' \sin \beta' = \frac{1}{2} \cdot a' b' \sin \gamma' = \frac{1}{2} \cdot b' c' \sin \alpha'$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001